

A Critical Review of:
Evaluating Integrated Watershed Management using Multiple Criteria Analysis – a case study at
Chittagong Hill Tracts in Bangladesh (Biswas, S., et al., 2012)¹

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Part 1: Introduction and background

At my request several papers were suggested to me by Justin Williams, our lead instructor, after the first peer-reviewed article was discovered to be inadequate with significant data and logic gaps. Of the choices I chose this article, which was published in 2012 in the Springer journal *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. In it, the authors use multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) to evaluate alternatives for the implementation of Integrated Watershed Management, with a case study example in the Chittagong Hill area of Bangladesh.

The watershed is an area of extreme topographic relief, which has resulted in severe soil erosion, and produced harmful effects to the aquatic ecosystem downstream. Degradation of surface water quality and the associated degradation of ecosystems. In addition, food security is a concern as less topsoil is available for agricultural.

If no action is taken to manage the watershed, eventually the agricultural activities will become unfeasible, and soil from erosion will eventually destroy the aquatic ecosystems, and any economic interests that may depend on them. Essentially, food production and downstream aquatic ecosystems will collapse.

Part 2: Summarize your selected paper or case study in terms of the MCDA steps covered in class.

2a. Identify the principal participants in the decision process, as identified in paper. These should include at least one decision maker and at least two stakeholder groups. What are the priorities of each participant?

No clear definite decision maker was identified by the authors in this paper. However, several stakeholder groups (referred to the paper as the *informant group* were identified and are listed below with the corresponding decision making priority. Based on my analysis of the paper, apparent stakeholder *decision making priorities* are provided below as none was provided in the paper.

<u>Stakeholder</u>	<u>Decision Making Priority</u>
Local farmers	Farming Sustainability
Resource Managers	Resource Conservation (forestry?)
Watershed Specialists	Watershed Conservation
Civil Engineers	Soil Stability and Erosion Mitigation
University Scientists (from forestry and environmental science)	Environmental and forestry sustainability

¹ Biswas, S., et al., 2012. *Evaluating Integrated Watershed Management using multiple criteria analysis – a case study at Chittagong Hill Tracts in Bangladesh*. Environ. Monit. Assess. 184:2741-2761, Springer Science and Business Media B.V.

2b. List and describe the attributes, goals, objectives, and decision criteria that the authors used in the paper. [Discuss whether the criteria were qualitative or quantitative.] Were the criteria structured in a value tree (criteria categories and individual criteria)? Did the authors neglect to include any criteria that you feel should have been included? If so, what are they and why are they important?

Criteria used by the authors are *qualitative*; that is, none of the criteria were listed with specific measurement units and required maximum or minimum achievement levels. Rather they generally described a broad range of desirable outcomes but lacked the specific to be used as measurement tools.

Table 1 below lists and describes the goals, attributes, objectives, and criteria presented in the paper. The information presented was derived (and in some cases *interpreted* where ambiguities were encountered) from the original paper. For example, under the Policy criterion the core components describing the criterion are listed directly under the Policy entry in the table.

The authors did present a value tree which included criteria categories and the respective individual criterion.

Based on my review of the paper, the authors failed to recognize the *integrated* nature of integrated watershed management. The alternatives the authors developed were too narrow in scope, lacking an integration components necessary for an integrated watershed management program. Lacking additional information to more fully understand and describe the real objectives of *this* watershed management program, I conclude either of two possibilities are true:

- 1) the *actual* goal is not *integrated watershed management*, or
- 2) the authors do not understand what integrated watershed management means

Upon review of the authors' alternatives (management strategies), the associated values, weights, and criteria, I think most of the necessary elements are present to rationally describe an integrated program. However, a *combination* of alternatives would be a better choice for an *integrated program* with *cross-sector* interventions and goals. For example, as the authors suggest in the results of their AHP analysis taken alone alternative MS-1 Biodiversity Conservation Strategy scores highest in utility; but this one choice falls well short of what is required for an integrated approach. What is needed to improve the likelihood of success is a combination of the authors proposed alternatives.

To further increase the likelihood of success, I offer some additional ideas for inclusion. Important criteria I see lacking are:

- establishment of a comprehensive geographic information system and database
- mapping and surveying of watersheds, land ownership and uses, agriculture cropping details
- water use demand projections and water resource inventory
- more detailed involvement goals and requirements for local stakeholder education, decision process involvement, and minorities and women inclusion

The lack of integration apparent in the authors work, the deficiencies described above informed the process of developing a *new alternative* (MO-7) Comprehensive Watershed Management, described later in this report.

Table 1. Goal, Attributes, Objectives, and Criteria

Goal	Attributes	Objectives	Criteria
<i>Integrated Watershed Management</i>	<p><i>Policy:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Legislative framework -Institutional framework - Management regulations -Scientific framework -Decision making <p><i>Economic:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Farming income -State income <p><i>Ecologic:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Soil fertility -Biodiversity -Water quality -Watershed Health <p><i>Risks:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Soil erosion -Illegal resource extraction -Flooding 	<p><i>Policy:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increase legislative and institutional frameworks -Increase management regulations -Increase scientific framework -Enhance decision protocols <p><i>Economic:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increase farm income -Increase State income <p><i>Ecologic:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increase soil fertility -Increase biodiversity -Protect water quality -Protect watershed health <p><i>Risks:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Prevent soil erosion -Prevent illegal resource extraction -Prevent flooding 	<p><i>Policy:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ownership and use rights -Strong law enforcement capability -Political support, awareness at local/national levels -Strengthen multilevel institution -Acceleration and expansion of current activities -Existence of watershed management regulations -Emergence of watershed management group -Skilled scientific research capacities -Well-defined precautionary and protective measures -Exchange of technology and expertise knowledge -Local people's and stakeholder's participation and cooperation <p><i>Economic:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Possibility of local incentives/subsidies -Net income from farming/forestry/alternative products -Maximum utilization of resources -Compliance of international protocol <p><i>Ecologic:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Growth potential (fertility of soil) for forest products -Growth potential (fertility of soil) for agricultural production -Conservation of floral and faunal richness -Reduction of threatened patented right -Improved surface water quality -Improved groundwater quality -Water crisis are reduced -Survey of existing threatened watershed -Planning watershed management <p><i>Risks:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Appropriate soil and water conservation measures -Construction of cross dams with bioengineering technology -Sloping land management with best practices -Reporting and handling illegal extraction of resources -Separate forest plantation for supplying excessive demand of industry by their cost -Formulating solutions for flooding problems -Planned activities are implemented

Note: Some terminology used in the paper differ from that were used in the class. For example, the authors at times refer to *informants* (instead of *decision makers* and *stakeholders*) as the source of information for the decision analysis process. In this assessment and re-analysis work I have attempted to translate the authors terminology and approach consistent with what we used in this course.

2c. List and describe the alternatives that the authors considered. How were they created?

Table 2 below list the alternatives considered by the authors. The alternatives were formulated by consulting with *local experts*. A no action alternative, i.e., MS-0, was considered (see Table 2).

Table 2. Alternatives¹

MS-0: Business as Usual strategy reflecting the Current Situation
MS-1: Biodiversity Conservation Strategy
MS-2: Flood Control Strategy
MS-3: Soil and Water Quality Conservation Strategy
MS-4: Indigenous Knowledge Conservation Strategy
MS-5: Income-generation Watershed Conservation Strategy
MS-6: Landscape Conservation Strategy

¹ The original paper refers to Management Strategies (MS) instead of alternatives.

2d. Describe/explain the performance metrics or other ways in which the authors assessed alternatives with respect to criteria.

Criteria developed by the authors (numbered 1.1 through 6.2) to measure the proposed alternatives (referred to as *management strategies* in the original paper) were developed through collaboration and discussions with stakeholders and advisors (p. 2745). The authors, in their Table 4 (**Attachment A**) applied *qualitative* ranking of each criterion based on consultations with stakeholders and advisors.

For this re-analysis and expansion of the original work, I applied a simple *more is better* numerical conversion to the published qualitative measure (a copy of the original table showing the conversion work is included in **Attachment A**). The resulting table of numerical performance levels is presented *in the required text format* as Table 3 (next page).

2d.a. Did the authors address uncertainty in performance levels, if so, how?

The authors did not explicitly address uncertainty in the performance levels. However, the authors did perform a sensitivity analysis on the AHP results. The analysis identified the relative sensitivity of each proposed management strategy by systematically varying the weights assigned to each criterion.

2e. Conduct Dominance Analysis.

All of the Alternatives were non-dominated, except the *no action* Alternative (MS-0) which was dominated by all of the proposed Alternatives (MS-1 through MS-6) (**Attachment B**).

Table 3. Performance Matrix

Performance Matrix (based on Table 4, p. 2751, copy of Table 4 is included in Attachment A)

All are more is better

	Individual Criteria																					
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	2.1	2.2	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	6.1	6.2
<i>Wgt</i>	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.075	0.075	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.075	0.075
<i>Alt</i>																						
MS-0	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.300	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.300	0.100	0.300	0.300	0.300	0.100	0.300	0.100
MS-1	0.500	0.100	0.500	0.700	1.000	0.700	0.700	0.500	0.700	0.700	0.500	0.500	0.500	0.500	0.300	0.300	0.700	0.300	0.500	0.100	0.300	0.100
MS-2	0.100	0.900	0.900	0.300	0.100	0.500	0.300	0.100	0.500	0.300	0.100	0.500	0.100	0.300	0.300	0.100	0.300	0.300	0.500	0.300	0.300	0.300
MS-3	0.700	0.300	0.500	0.300	0.300	0.500	0.300	0.500	0.500	0.500	0.100	0.500	0.300	0.100	0.500	0.300	0.500	0.700	0.300	0.500	0.300	0.500
MS-4	0.900	0.900	0.900	0.300	0.900	0.300	0.500	0.300	0.700	0.100	0.300	0.700	0.100	0.100	0.500	0.300	0.900	0.500	0.300	0.100	0.300	0.500
MS-5	0.900	0.700	0.900	0.300	0.100	0.700	0.500	0.300	0.100	0.700	0.500	0.500	0.300	0.100	0.500	0.500	0.900	0.700	0.500	0.700	0.700	0.500
MS-6	0.900	0.700	0.700	0.300	0.100	0.300	0.300	0.300	0.100	0.700	0.500	0.700	0.500	0.100	0.500	0.500	0.900	0.900	0.500	0.700	0.700	0.700

2f. Conduct Tradeoff Analysis.

A tradeoff analysis (MCDA Step 6) was performed on three management strategy (MS) pairs against the 22 criterion using procedures described in Course Note 4 (Williams, J., ND, pp.6-9). The MS pairs evaluated were: MS-1/MS-2; MS-3/MS-4, MS-5/MS-6. Performance Path diagrams were prepared for each criterion pair and are include in **Attachment C**.

An analysis of the performance path diagrams reveals the following tradeoff relationships.

- **Performance Path Diagram No. 1:** MS-1 generally out performed with measureable tradeoff versus MS-2 across most of the 22 criterion. For example, MS-1 exhibited substantial tradeoff versus MS-2 under Criterion 1.5 Proper Decision Making Mechanism; for every one unit of Criterion 1.5 for MS-2, 9 units of Criterion 1.5 was generated under MS-1.
- **Performance Path Diagram No. 2:** Generally, MS-3 and MS-4 performed about the same, exhibiting high and low performance levels. However, exceptions were noted: for every three units of criterion 1.2 and 1.5 under MS-3, 4 units of the respective criterions were generated under MS-4.
- **Performance Path Diagram No. 3:** There are many similarities between MS-5 and MS-6. A notable exception is Criterion 2.1 Contribution Margin / Net Income of Farmers, where MS-6 exhibited a moderate tradeoff with MS-5; for every two units of Criterion 2.1 under MS-6, 5 units of Criterion 2.1 were generated by MS-6.

2g. Identify which MCDA aggregation method(s) the authors used.

The authors used the Analytical Hierarchy Process (APH) to perform an MCDA analysis.

Part 3: Extend the paper’s problem in an original way by developing one new alternative to add to the analysis. The new alternative you create might be one that performs well in a criterion in which none of the existing alternatives does particularly well. Or, your new alternative may address other areas that the authors missed, such as an alternative that is not best in any criterion but has acceptable performance in most or all criteria.

3a. Describe your new alternative in terms of its components and attributes, and explain why it is important to include it. Estimate your new alternative’s performance level in each of the criteria. Your new alternative must be non-dominated with respect to the other alternatives.

The existing six alternatives (management strategies in the original paper), i.e., MS-1 through MS-6, are too narrowly focused to comprehensively address the challenges effecting the Chittagong Hill area watershed of Bangladesh. To address this significant deficiency, I developed a new alternative (management strategy) (MO) MO-7 – Comprehensive Watershed Management.

MO-7 presents a unified approach to truly integrated watershed management, something the existing six proposed management strategies do not.

MO-7 Key Components include:

- Technical definition of the watershed boundaries

- Mapping/surveying of all land uses, land ownership, surface water features, soil type, topography, water use, crop type (for agricultural uses)
- Establishment of a comprehensive geographic information system (GIS) and database to hold and track the watershed information; the GIS data will be open and accessible by anyone from the Internet, i.e., it will be web-enabled and all data access will be available free of charge.
- Prepare a comprehensive watershed management plan
- Develop goal and strategies for sustainable (long term) watershed management
- Develop government legislation to support, protect, and enforce the watershed
- Form watershed user groups (with emphasis on local and minority involvement) to guide the development of the elements above

The performance level of MO-7 was estimated for each of the 22 criterion (**Attachment D**). Using a pairwise comparison methodology, MO-7 was determined to be non-dominated.

Part 4: Apply one of the three MCDA aggregation methods presented in the course (Additive Weighting, AHP, or ELECTRE). Develop weights, value functions, and any needed parameters, as required by the method. Identify weights, value functions, etc. that reflect the priorities and preferences of one of the participants (decision maker or stakeholder) based on your judgment and on any evidence provided in the paper.

4a. Determine utility scores and rankings, or outranking relationships, as appropriate for the MCDA method. Show your work and calculations, and explain what you have done in each step. DO NOT simply hand in a spreadsheet or table of numbers with no explanation. If it seems appropriate, you may use a set of weights, etc. that was listed in the paper or case study. However, your MCDA application must be original; it may not duplicate one of the MCDA methods from the paper. For example, if AHP was used in the paper, then you must apply either Additive Weighting or ELECTRE, but not AHP.

MCDA method chosen: The Additive Weighting Method (AWM) was selected to analyze the eight alternatives (management strategies) (six original alternatives, one new alternative, and the original *no action* alternative),

Weighting: Twenty-two criteria were used to re-evaluate all of the alternatives. The *weighting* applied to each of the criterion was derived from the original paper; the author derived the *weights* based on information received from the decision maker(s) (not clearly defined in the paper), stakeholder groups, and local experts.

In performing the AWM, a two-step calculation process was used. In Step 1, Value Functions were developed for each performance level. In Step 2, a *Utility Score* was calculated for each alternative (management strategy). Both Step 1 and Step 2 are described below.

Step 1:

Value Functions were determined for each of the performance levels within each of the 22 criterion. Using the methodology described in Course Note 5 (Williams, J., ND, pp. 1-6). Since each of the criteria are *more is better* and *linear* the following equation from Course Note 5 was used to calculate the *value function*.

$$V_j(PL_{ij}) = ((PL_{ij} - PL_{jmin}) / (PL_{jmax} - PL_{jmin}))$$

where,

V	Value function
PL	Performance Level
PLjmin	minimum Performance Level across all 22 criteria for each alternative
PLjmax	maximum Performance Level across all 22 criteria for each alternative

A copy of the spreadsheet showing the results of the *value function* calculations is included in **Attachment E**.

Step 2:

The *Utility Score (Ui)* for each of the eight alternatives was developed using calculation methodology described in Course Note 5 (Williams, J., ND, pp. 1-19). The following equation from Course Note 5 was used to calculate a *UI* for each of the alternatives.

$$U_i = \sum_{j=1,n} W_j \times V_j(PL_{ij})$$

where,

Ui	Utility Score
W	Weight
V	Value
PL	Performance Level

A copy of the spreadsheet showing the results of the *Utility Index* calculations is included in **Attachment F**. The spreadsheet calculation identified a best compromise alternative (BCA), i.e., the alternative with the highest *Utility Score*. The results of the *Ui* calculation are also repeated below.

<u>Utility Scores</u>	
MS-0	0.229
MS-1	0.401
MS-2	0.290
MS-3	0.501
MS-4	0.432
MS-5	0.503
MS-6	0.509
MS-7	0.559 (BCA)

According to the Utility Scores obtained from the AWM calculations, the new alternative (MS-7) is a best compromise alternative, not MS-1 as the authors concluded in the original paper.

4b. Present the results/ outcomes of your MCDA aggregation method, and compare them to the results obtained by the authors using other aggregation methods. Are the results using your method consistent with the authors' results based on other MCDA methods? If not, where do the discrepancies lie? How did your new alternative perform? Does one alternative emerge as being a clear "best compromise alternative"? How would environmental security likely be improved by implementing the best compromise alternative? [If applicable: Do the results indicate that the participants agree or disagree about what the most-preferred alternative is? Is there a good candidate for a "best consensus alternative"?]

My results using the AWM were different from the authors (using the AHP method). I calculated MS-7 (the new alternative) is the best compromise alternative, scoring the highest Utility Score. The original paper concluded that MS-1 the biodiversity Conservation Strategy was the BCA. Interestingly, my AWM calculations did not support the authors conclusion for MS-1; rather my AWM calculations showed MS-6 as the next best (next highest scoring) alternative.

Environmental Security will be improved by implementing MS-7 (the new alternative and BCA) because it is the best option for moving toward the goal of integrated watershed management; it is design to be comprehensive and facilitate involvement across key areas in the development process, with emphasis on grassroots stakeholders, minorities, and women. All of the other alternatives are too narrow in scope and therefore will fail to promote integration of people and processes.

4c. Identify and describe ways in which performance-level scale type may affect the validity and usefulness of your analysis. Explain to prospective decision makers the nature of these same measurement-theoretic considerations and how they may affect the relative trustworthiness of your choice of MCDA tools in guiding the decision-making process.

I discovered that performance level scale influences the outcome of the AWM calculations. Specifically, if performance levels are consistently higher (as compared to other alternatives) the likelihood that the alternative with the higher performance level will be the BCA is increased. Knowing this, there is an importance placed on transparency of the MCDA process, the integrity of the preference and values solicitation processes, and how MCDA is explained to decision makers and the effected public.

When I use MCDA (AWM or other method), I will clearly and fully explain to the decision makers (before the start of the project) that MCDA is a decision support process; it provides an opportunity to closely examine the core components of a decision – to identify values and preferences, and to think critically and rationally about the means to achieve a goal; and importantly, it creates an environment where new alternatives or combination of alternatives can be developed – ones that were perhaps not initially envisioned.

Ultimately, the decision on which alternative to select rests with the decision maker.

ATTACHMENT A

Performance Matrix

Table 4 Qualitative assessment of six management strategies based on principles and criteria and determination of intensity of influencing verifier by six management strategies

Principle	Criteria	MS-0	MS-I	MS-II	MS-III	MS-IV	MS-V	MS-VI
1. Policy planning	1.1 Proper legislative framework	→1	∅5	→1	∅7	∅4	∅6	∅9
	1.2 Proper institutional framework	→1	11	∅4	13	∅9	∅7	∅7
	1.3 Watershed management regulations	→1	∅5	∅3	∅5	∅9	∅9	∅7
	1.4 Proper scientific framework	13	∅1	13	13	13	13	13
	1.5 Proper decision-making mechanism	→1	∅10	→1	13	13	13	13
Influence on verifiers	2.1 Contribution margin/net income of farmers	65	50	19	27	21	25	20
	2.2 Income generation for region/state	→1	∅7	∅5	∅5	13	∅7	13
Influence on verifiers	3.1 Maintenance of soil fertility	13	13	4	8	5	10	3
	3.2 Maintenance of biodiversity	→1	∅5	→1	∅5	13	13	13
	3.3 Maintenance of water quality	→1	∅7	∅5	∅5	∅7	∅7	∅7
	3.4 Identification of degraded sites in watershed	→1	∅5	→1	→1	13	13	∅5
Influence on verifiers	4.1 Reduction of soil erosion	31	31	6	11	9	14	15
	4.2 Reduction of illegal extraction	→1	∅5	∅5	∅5	∅7	∅5	∅7
	4.3 Reduction of flash flood	→1	∅5	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1
Influence on verifiers	5.1 Education and training	18	13	5	7	8	7	12
	5.2 Fuelwood production	→1	13	→1	∅5	→1	→1	→1
	5.3 Possibility to produce food	→1	13	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1
	5.4 Use of innovative technology	→1	13	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1
	5.5 Empowerment of women	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1
	5.6 Possibilities for settlement	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1
Influence on verifiers	6.1 Forest management plan	45	15	6	29	26	39	39
	6.2 Evaluation and monitoring	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1	→1
Influence on verifiers		19	2	4	8	5	14	19

→ no difference, / slight improvement, ∅ moderate improvement, ∅ strong improvement, ∅ very strong improvement, ∅∅ extreme influence or improvement

1 3 5 7

ATTACHMENT B

Dominance Analysis

Dominance Analysis
All are more is better

Alt	Individual Criteria														Status									
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	2.1	2.2	3	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3		5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	6.1	6.2	
MS-0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	Dominated by MS-1, MS-2, MS-3, MS-4, MS-5, MS-6
MS-1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.7	1.00	0.7	0.7	1	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	Non-dominated
MS-2	0.1	0.9	0.9	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.3	0	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	Non-dominated
MS-3	0.7	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	1	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.5	Non-dominated
MS-4	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.5	0	0.7	0.1	0.3	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.9	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	Non-dominated
MS-5	0.9	0.7	0.9	0.3	0.1	0.7	0.5	0	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.7	Non-dominated
MS-6	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3	0	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.9	0.9	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	Non-dominated

ATTACHMENT C

Performance Path Diagrams (3)

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Part 2, Q.F

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Performance Path Diagram No. 1

Performance Path

COMPARISON OF MS-1 and MS-2

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Part 2, Q. F

Performance Path Diagram No 2

PERFORMANCE PATH

COMPARISON OF MS-3 and MS-4

(20)

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Part 2, Q.F

Sd/10

Performance Path Diagram No.3

PERFORMANCE PATH

COMPARISON OF MS-5 and MS-6

ATTACHMENT D

Alternative 7 (Management Strategy MO-7) Performance Levels

Part 4
A.

**New Alternative (MS-7): Weighting shown is estimated
Decision Maker Selected: Professor**

All are more is better

Alt	Individual Criteria																						
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	2.1	2.2	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	6.1	6.2	
MS-0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1
MS-1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.7	1.00	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1
MS-2	0.1	0.9	0.9	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
MS-3	0.7	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.5
MS-4	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.7	0.1	0.3	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.9	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.5
MS-5	0.9	0.7	0.9	0.3	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.5
MS-6	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.9	0.9	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
MS-7	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.7	0.5	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.4	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.9

Notes:

MS-7 Comprehensive Watershed Management
Individual Criteria performance levels estimated

(7)

ATTACHMENT E

Value Function Calculation

Part 4, A
UI Calculation

Step 1: Value Function Calculation

All Criteria, i.e., 1.1 through 6.2, are more is better

C1.1 through C6.2 are linear, so:
Step 1: $V(P_{ij1}) = ((P_{ijmax} - P_{ijmin}) / (P_{ijmax} - P_{ijmin}))$
Step 2: $U_i = W_1 V_1(P_{i11}) + W_2 V_2(P_{i21}) + \dots + W_n V_n(P_{in1})$

Alt	Individual Criteria																						
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	2.1	2.2	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	6.1	6.2	
Weight (W)	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.075	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.075	0.075	
MS-0	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000
MS-1	0.444	0.000	0.444	0.667	0.000	0.667	0.667	0.444	0.667	0.667	0.444	0.444	0.444	0.444	0.222	0.222	0.667	0.222	0.444	0.000	0.222	0.000	0.000
MS-2	0.000	1.000	1.000	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.250	0.250	0.500	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250
MS-3	1.000	0.333	0.667	0.333	0.333	0.667	0.333	0.667	0.667	0.667	0.000	0.667	0.333	0.000	0.667	0.333	0.667	1.000	0.333	0.667	0.333	0.667	0.667
MS-4	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.250	1.000	0.250	0.500	0.250	0.750	0.000	0.250	0.750	0.000	0.000	0.500	0.250	1.000	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.250	0.500	0.500
MS-5	1.000	0.750	1.000	0.250	0.000	0.750	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.750	0.500	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.500	1.000	0.750	0.500	0.500	0.750	0.750	0.250
MS-6	1.000	0.750	0.750	0.250	0.000	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.750	0.500	0.750	0.500	0.000	0.500	0.500	1.000	1.000	0.500	0.750	0.750	0.750	0.750
MS-7	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.200	0.200	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.600	0.200	0.800	0.600	0.800	0.000	0.600	0.800	1.000	0.600	0.800	0.800	1.000

= New Alternative with estimated values

Completed

ATTACHMENT F
Utility Score Calculation

C1.1 through C6.2 are linear, so:
 Step1: $V1(Pl1i) = ((Pjmax - Plimin) / (Pljmax - Pljmin))$
 Step2: $U_i = W1V1(Pl1i) + W2V2(Pl1i) + Wn Vn(Plin), \dots$

Step 2: UI Calculation

	Individual Criteria																						
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	2.1	2.2	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	6.1	6.2	
Weight (W)	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.075	0.075	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.075	0.075	
Alt																							
MS-0	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	
MS-1	0.444	0.000	0.444	0.667	0.000	0.667	0.667	0.444	0.667	0.667	0.444	0.444	0.444	0.444	0.222	0.222	0.667	0.222	0.444	0.000	0.222	0.000	
MS-2	0.000	1.000	1.000	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.250	0.250	0.500	0.250	0.250	0.250	
MS-3	1.000	0.333	0.667	0.333	0.333	0.667	0.333	0.667	0.667	0.667	0.000	0.667	0.333	0.000	0.667	0.333	0.667	1.000	0.333	0.667	0.333	0.667	
MS-4	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.250	1.000	0.250	0.500	0.250	0.750	0.000	0.250	0.750	0.000	0.000	0.500	0.250	1.000	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.250	0.500	
MS-5	1.000	0.750	1.000	0.250	0.000	0.750	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.750	0.500	0.500	0.250	0.000	0.500	0.500	1.000	0.750	0.500	0.500	0.750	0.250	
MS-6	1.000	0.750	0.750	0.250	0.000	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.750	0.500	0.750	0.500	0.500	0.500	0.500	1.000	1.000	0.500	0.500	0.750	0.750	
MS-7	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.200	0.200	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.600	0.200	0.800	0.600	0.800	0.000	0.600	0.800	1.000	0.600	0.800	1.000	

Utility Scores

Alt	
MS-0	0.229
MS-1	0.401
MS-2	0.290
MS-3	0.501
MS-4	0.432
MS-5	0.503
MS-6	0.509
MS-7	0.559
BCA	